

HOME ECONOMICS STUDENTS LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) FACILITIES FOR LEARNING IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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Home Economics Education, ICT Awareness, Colleges of Education, North Eastern Nigeria and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Facilities.

Abstract: *Home Economics, also known as domestic science or family and consumer sciences, is a subject that encompasses various aspects of home management and human development. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays a vital role in the development of any nation. The purpose of the study investigated the Home Economics Students Level of Awareness of ICT Facilities for Learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. Survey Research Design was adopted for the study and the population of the study comprised of all the Home Economics Students in Colleges of Education in North Eastern, from which a sample of 185 Home Economics Students were selected through a purposive sampling technique for study from four College of Education. Students ICT Awareness Questionnaire (SIAQ) with reliability index of 0.786 was adopted and used for study. The data collected were descriptively analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research question, while the research hypothesis was tested using independent sample t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that among others that Home Economic Students are partially aware of the available ICT facilities within the schools in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria. Furthermore, the Home Economics Students are faced with numerous challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. It was recommended that management of the Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria should intensify their awareness creation for all students through ICT orientations. In addition to the awareness creation, management should organize information literacy training for all students irrespective of their level of knowledge in ICT.*

Introduction

Home Economics, also known as domestic science or family and consumer sciences, is a

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course that encompasses various aspects of home management and personal development. It focuses on areas like human development, personal and family finances, consumer issues, housing, nutrition, food preparation, and textiles.

Home Economics is one of the vocational courses that is concerned with the social welfare of individuals and families. It deals with all aspects of family life and prepares the learner for effective employment in an occupation. Similarly, Home Economics as a vocational course draws her knowledge from many areas of disciplines such as biological, physical and social science some of her areas include food and nutrition, clothing and textiles, home management, consumer education, home furnishing and interior decoration, child development and family relation (Anyakoha and Eluwa, 2011).

Key Areas of Home Economics: Human Development this includes child development, family relations, and understanding the stages of life. Personal and Family Finances this include Managing budgets, saving, investing, and understanding consumer behavior. Housing and Interior Design this include learning about different housing types, home maintenance, and interior design principles. Food Preparation and Nutrition this include understanding healthy eating habits, food safety and cooking techniques. Textiles and Apparel this include

sewing, garment construction, and understanding fabric properties. Consumer Issues this include making informed purchasing decisions, understanding advertising, and consumer rights.

In Nigeria schools and colleges, Home Economics is broadly divided into three areas food and nutrition, home management and clothing and textiles. Each component is often taught as a subject at all levels and is dedicated to the task of helping individuals learn better those behavioral patterns and skills that will enable them to fulfill effectively their roles as family members as well as preparing the learn to be gainfully employed through the acquired skills they obtained.

Information Communication Technology (ICT) has changed the way we do things in all aspect of human endeavors. Effective learning depends on the quality of teaching, instructional materials available and students' awareness of available Information Communication Technology (ICT) facilities in the learning centers (Okereke, Garba & Dauda, 2020). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays a major role in the individual professional lives. As a result of this technological revolution there are increasing demands for learning centers to integrate this technology to enhance the teaching-learning process.

Information and Communication Technology can be defined as a diverse set of electronic

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technologies and technological tools and resources used to communicate, create, store, disseminate and manage information (Ikwuka, 2013). Similarly, Wertlen (2014) defines ICT as a general term that describes any technology that helps to produce, manipulate, store, communicate, or disseminate information. Information and communication technology (ICT) is a process of creating, processing, storage, retrieval and dissemination of information through usage of computers and telecommunications.

Information Communication Technology development has great influence on all sectors of life. Information and Communication Technology has reformed the way we do things (Fadip, Balarabe and Ya'u, 2018).

ICT in education has the potential to transform teaching and learning among students at all level of education. ICT has been an instrument for achieving social, economic, educational, scientific and technological development (Adedeji, 2010).

Information and Communication Technology has become an important part of most educational organizations all over the world and there is no doubt that ICT provides productive teaching and learning in order to increase learners' creative and intellectual resources especially in today's information society (Ikwuka, 2013). Based on the forgone submission, this present study will investigate

the Home Economics Students Level of Awareness of ICT Facilities for Learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Home Economics, also known as domestic science or family and consumer sciences, is a subject that encompasses various aspects of home management and personal development. It focuses on areas like human development, personal and family finances, consumer issues, housing, nutrition, food preparation, and textiles. It was observed by the research that effective utilization of ICT in teaching and learning depends on the availability and awareness of these facilities and teachers' competence in using them. Also lack of adequate computer literate teachers, irregular power supply and inadequate funding are another set of obstacle militating against effective utilization of ICT facilities in teaching and learning Home Economics. Based on the forgone submission, this present study will investigate the Home Economics Students Level of Awareness on Information Communication Technology (ICT) Facilities for Learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Objectives: The objectives of this study are:

1. To identify the ICT facilities available for learning by Home Economics students' in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

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2. To ascertain the level of Home Economics Students' Awareness of ICT Facilities for learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

3. To highlight the challenges Home Economics Students' face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The corresponding null hypotheses to the research question is stated thus:

Ho₁. There is no significant difference between the level of male and female Home Economics Students Awareness on ICT Facilities learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

Ho₂. There is no significant difference between the level challenges of male and female Home Economic Students face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria

Methodology

The research design for this study is survey research design. The population for the study was all of Home Economics Students in the College of Education North East Geo-political zone of Nigeria. A sample of 187 Home Economics Students was selected from 4 Colleges of Education in the area of study through purposive sampling technique. The Students ICT Awareness Questionnaire (SIAQ) was adapted from Fadip, Balarabe and Ya'u, (2018) and used for data collection. The SIAQ had an internal consistency reliability of 0.786. The data collected were analyzed using mean, percentage and standard deviation. Means and Percentage was used to answer research questions one to three while inferential statistics was used to answer hypotheses one and two.

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Research 1: What are the ICT facilities available for learning for Home Economics Students in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria?

Result of the Study

Table 1: ICT facilities available for learning for Home Economics Students in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	Available	Not Available
1	Desktop/Laptop Computers	147(79.46)	38(20.54)
2	Handhelds/Tablets computers (iPad)/other mobile devices	157(84.86)	28(15.14)
3	Smart/Interactive White Board (e.g. Triumph Board, Genee touch etc.)	124(82.19)	33(17.81)
4	Digital Camera	114(61.6)	71(38.4)
5	Hard Disk Drive (External)	128(69.2)	57(30.8)
6	Flash Drive	108(56.4)	77(41.6)
7	CD/DVD	105(56.5)	80(43.2)
8	Internet	161(87.03)	24(12.97)
9	Educational Website	158(85.41)	27(14.59)
10	E-mail (Gmail, Yahoo Mail etc.)	107(57.8)	78(42.2)
11	Digital Signage	100(54.1)	85(45.9)
12	Video Conferencing Facilities	22(11.89)	163(88.11)
13	Microsoft Office Packages (e.g. MS Word, MS Excel, MS PowerPoint, MS Access)	105(56.6)	80(43.2)
14	Graphic Packages (e.g. Adobe Photoshop, Corel Draw, AutoCAD)	82(44.32)	103(55.68)
15	G Suites (e.g. Google Docs, Google sheets, Google slides, Google forms etc.)	25(13.51)	160(86.49)
16	Learning Management Systems (e.g. Moodle)	35(18.92)	148(81.08)

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Table 1 showed that the following 1,2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 10, 11 & 13 ICT facilities available for learning for Home Economics Students in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria

while item 12, 14, 15 & 16 are not available for learning for Home Economics Students in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

Research 2: What is the level of Home Economics Students Awareness of ICT

Facilities for learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of Home Economics Students Awareness of ICT Facilities for learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Desktop/Laptop Computers	2.13	.638	VMA
2	Handhelds/Tablets computers (iPad)/other mobile devices	2.06	.673	VMA
3	Smart/Interactive White Board (e.g. Triumph Board, Genee touch etc.)	2.13	.612	PA
4	Digital Camera	1.98	.651	PA
5	Hard Disk Drive (External)	2.08	.638	PA
6	Flash Drive	2.14	.708	PA
7	CD/DVD	1.96	.718	VMA
8	Internet	1.92	.741	VMA
9	Educational Website	1.83	.717	PA
10	E-mail (Gmail, Yahoo Mail etc.)	2.12	.757	NA
11	Digital Signage	2.14	.753	PA
12	Video Conferencing Facilities	2.08	.797	NA
13	Microsoft Office Packages (e.g. MS Word, MS Excel, MS PowerPoint, MS Access)	2.30	.688	PA
14	Graphic Packages (e.g. Adobe Photoshop, Corel Draw, AutoCAD)	2.25	.696	NA
15	G Suites (e.g. Google Docs, Google sheets, Google slides, Google forms etc.)	2.22	.673	NA
16	Learning Management Systems (e.g. Moodle)	2.15	.579	NA
	Total	2.09		PA

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KEY: Not Aware (NA) = 1.00-1.49, Partially Aware (PA) = 1.50-2.49, and Very Much Aware (VMA) = 2.50-3.00

Table 2 showed the items 1, 2, 7 & 8, had mean ratings within the range of 2.50-3.00 (VMA). This means that the Home Economics Students are very much aware of ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. On the other hand, items 3, 4, 5, 6, 9, 11 & 13 had means ratings within the range of 1.50-2.49 (PA), which means that the Home Economics Students are partially aware of availability of these ICT facilities for learning in

Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. While items 10, 12, 14, 15 & 16 had mean ratings within the range of 1.00-1.49 (NA), which means that the Home Economics Students are not aware of the available ICT facilities. The items had a grand mean of 2.09 which falls under the mean rating of (PA), which means that the Home Economics Students are partially aware of the available ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

Research 3: What are the challenges Home Economics Students face during

learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 3: Challenges Home Economics Students face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Poor working condition of computers	2.78	1.082	Agreed
2	Lack of access of Internet	2.60	1.064	Agreed
3	Non availability of the require software	2.78	1.004	Agreed
4	Lack of technical support	2.61	1.123	Agreed
5	Virus threat	2.73	1.007	Agreed
6	Slow speed of computers	2.65	1.037	Agreed
7	Signal problem in Internet	2.61	1.093	Agreed
8	Lack of technical support for maintenance of systems	2.78	1.004	Agreed
9	Use of unlicensed software	2.68	1.059	Agreed
10	Outdated hardware and software systems	2.76	1.053	Agreed
11	Scarcity of educational software	2.80	1.036	Agreed
12	Limited time	2.68	.950	Agreed

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Total	2.71
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Table 3 showed the items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 & 12 had mean ratings above 2.50. This means that the Home Economics Students are faced with the above mention challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. **Ho₁. There is no significant difference between the level of male and female Home Economics**

Education in North Eastern Nigeria. The items had a grand mean of 2.71 Home Economics Students are faced with the above mention challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. **Students Awareness on ICT Facilities learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.**

Table 4: t-test Home Economics Students Awareness on ICT Facilities Learning in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria.

Group	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig	Decision
Male	26	34.88	2.69	-1.747	183	.082	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	159	35.79	2.42				

The result in Table 4 showed that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female Home Economic Students on the awareness of availability of ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria (t= -1.747, p>0.05).

Ho₂. There is no significant difference between the level challenges of male and female Home Economic Students face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria

Table 5: t-test showing difference between the level challenges of male and female Home Economic Students face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

Group	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig	Decision
Male	26	31.11	3.55	-2.085	183	.038	Ho ₂ Rejected
Female	159	32.69	3.56				

The result in Table 5 showed that there is statistically significant difference between male and female Home Economic Students face on the challenges face during learning with ICT

Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria (t= -2.085, p<0.05).

Summary of Major Findings

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1. Home Economic Students are partially aware of the available ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

2. Home Economic Students are faced with different kind of challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

3. There is no statistically significant difference between male and female Home Economic Students on the awareness of availability of ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

4. There is statistically significant difference between male and female Home Economic Students face on the challenges face during learning with ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that Home Economic Students are partially aware of the available ICT facilities for learning in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria, this finding coincides with that of Bradbury and Borchert (2010) who opined that most students were aware of and have basic to expert skills in reference managers, communication applications and open access journals. Also, the result of the study is in agreement with Saini, Bhakar, and Singh (2014)'s finding which indicates that majority of students were aware of information and communication technology service (ICTs) in the library.

Furthermore the result of the study revealed that Home Economic Students are faced with different kind of challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria is in agreement with Aduwa-Ogiegbaen and Iyamu (2005) identified lack of stable electricity, lack of relevant software, limited access to the Internet, inadequate telecommunication facilities, lack of human skills and knowledge, weak infrastructure, and lack of cost effective and reliable Internet connectivity as technological challenges in Nigeria.

Similarly, the finding of this study is agreement with that of Siddiquah & Salim (2017) Other problems participants faced at home were virus threat, signal problem in Internet, slow speed of computers, lack of access of Internet, lack of technical support, and poor working condition of computers. Students face more problems regarding the use of ICT at university than at home.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from this study is that Home Economic Students are partially aware of the available ICT facilities within the schools in Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria. Furthermore, the Home Economics Students are faced with numerous challenges during learning with ICT facilities in Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria

Recommendations

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Based on the result of the study it was recommended that:

1. Management of the Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria should intensify their awareness creation for all students through ICT orientations, user education as well as seminars and workshops.

2. In addition to the awareness creation, management should organize information

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literacy training for all students irrespective of their level of knowledge in ICT.

3. Finally, the study recommended that management of the Colleges of Education North Eastern Nigeria should find a way to acquire more ICT facilities and make them available and accessible to all students.

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